

THE METHODOLOGY OF FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE OF PRIMARY PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract: This thesis examines the factors affecting students' health. The main components of health are somatic, mental, physical and moral. The criteria that should be used in the physical education of the young generation are proposed.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, physical activity, spiritual and social well-being, individual human health, physical culture, somatic component, moral component.

Introduction.

Today's globalized world makes great demands on each individual's health. Therefore, the basics of healthy lifestyle formation in the educational process are more relevant than ever. The purpose of using the main factors of forming a healthy lifestyle in the educational process is to give students the opportunity to maintain their health during their studies in higher education and to form the necessary knowledge from it.

The realization of this goal directly depends on the following factors: priority directions of the educational process:

- organization of a rational educational process;
- reasonable organization of students' physical activity;
- system of work on formation of healthy lifestyle values.

Before considering the basics of healthy lifestyle formation, it is necessary to clarify which elements of the educational process can have a negative effect on the health of students of the specialty of primary education. This is primarily: a large number of topics on the table; the large size and complexity of the educational material; study; stressful control situations. An attentive teacher always notices external signs of mental and physical exhaustion of a student. Maintaining the health of students begins with the organization of the entire educational process. Thus, the following factors influence the health of students:

- ❖ decrease in physical activity;
- ❖ increased number of missed classes due to colds and illness;
- ❖ visual impairment, deterioration of mental health;
- ❖ incompatibility of stressful pedagogical tactics, teaching methods and technologies with students' functional capabilities;
- ❖ non-observance of elementary physiological and hygienic requirements for organization of educational process;
- ❖ parents' literacy in matters of students' health is insufficient;
- ❖ failures in the existing system of physical education;
- ❖ strengthening the educational process; functional illiteracy of the teacher in matters of health care and strengthening;
- ❖ lack of systematic work on forming the value of a healthy lifestyle.

Therefore, it is at this stage that a thorough and comprehensive scientific approach to the introduction of knowledge about the formation of a healthy lifestyle and the use of various effective forms of their organization in the educational process is necessary.

There are more than 300 definitions of the concept of "health". According to the definition of the World Health Organization, health is not only the absence of disease or physical infirmity, but also a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. There are many definitions of the concept of "health", the meaning of which is determined by the professional point of view of the authors. According to the definition adopted by the World Health Organization in September 1948: "health is not only the absence of disease and infirmity, but also a state of physical, mental and social well-being".

From a physiological point of view, the following formulas are defined:

- individual health of a person - the natural state of the body against the background of the absence of pathological changes, optimal connection with the environment, consistency of all functions;

- health care is a harmonious set of structural and functional information of the organism that is compatible with the environment and provides the body with optimal vital activity, as well as with full labor activity;

- individual health of a person is a harmonious unity of all metabolic processes in the body, which creates conditions for optimal life of all systems and subsystems of the body;

- health is the process of maintaining and developing biological, physiological, psychological functions, labor capacity and social activity with the maximum duration of a person's active life [V. P. Ghaznachiev, 2006].

Health is formed as a result of the interaction of external and internal factors:

- signs of personal health: specific and non-specific resistance to the effects of harmful factors;

- indicators of growth and development, the current functional state and potential of the organism and person;

- presence and degree of any disease or developmental defect;

- level of moral-will and value-motivational attitude.

Physical health is a natural state that occurs due to the normal functioning of all organs and systems of the body. If all the organs and systems work well, then the whole human body works and develops properly.

Mental health depends on the state of the brain, which is characterized by the level and quality of thinking, the development of attention and memory, the level of emotional stability, and the development of willpower.

Moral health is determined by the moral principles that are the basis of human social life, i.e. life in a certain human society. Characteristic signs of moral health of a person are, first of all, a conscious attitude to work, mastering cultural treasures, actively rejecting morals and customs that are contrary to the moral and legal way of life.

In order to study the issue of attitude towards a healthy lifestyle, we developed a questionnaire and conducted a survey among student youth and physical education teachers in order to determine the attitude of the respondents towards a healthy lifestyle. Only 50% of teachers use posters, pictures, diagrams and other additional visual materials in their classes to create a negative attitude towards bad habits and to form students' correct awareness of a healthy lifestyle. theoretical information about the benefits of physical education and sports is

given by 32% of teachers, 18% of teachers do not consider it important to spend time on theoretical information; 40% of teachers talk to their students about healthy lifestyle issues in their free time.

One of the leading places in the formation of a healthy lifestyle of future primary education teachers is the area of need and motivation, which allows them to join the process of health care and formation, for which it is known conditions must be created:

- provision of qualified specialists in the fields of psychology, pedagogy and sports;
- introduction of innovative approaches in the methodology of teaching physical culture, taking into account the physiological and mental qualities of each student, focusing on health technologies, psychological service, cooperation with medical specialists.

The use of the main criteria for the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the educational process leads to a decrease in the incidence of diseases among students, an improvement of the psychological climate among children and teachers, and actively involves the parents of schoolchildren in health promotion work. For teachers who have mastered the criteria of forming a healthy lifestyle, work will be easier and more interesting, because the problem of discipline will disappear and space will be opened for pedagogical creativity.

In addition, you should diversify the lesson program as much as possible, note which aspect interests each child the most and try to stimulate their personal interests in the future, use more forms and means of communication that cause the least negative reactions in lessons, in our opinion, a valuable note is the following: the greater use of speech means is communication, and among them are not only identification signals, but also the verbal method (covering).

Conclusion:

In order to effectively introduce the ideas of a healthy lifestyle into pedagogical practice, three problems must be solved:

1. Changing the teacher's outlook, attitude towards himself, life experience.
2. Change the teacher's attitude towards students. The teacher should fully accept the student as he is and on this basis try to understand what his abilities are.
3. Changing the teacher's attitude to the tasks of the educational process of health pedagogy, which includes not only the achievement of didactic goals, but also the development of students who are as healthy as possible.

A healthy lifestyle does not yet occupy the first place in the hierarchy of human needs and values in our society. Children should be taught to value, protect and strengthen their health from a very young age. The purpose of the above recommendations is to develop individual-oriented physical education and wellness activities that ensure the formation of healthy components of the child's personality development, to realize the need for physical and psychological self-defense, as well as the development of sports and positive motivation is to contribute to the promotion.

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